

ARCHITECTURE

ARCHITECTURAL HERITAGE AND NATIONAL IDENTITY FEATURES OF KARABAKH FROM ANCIENT TIMES TO THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES

Aygün Əliyeva Zəlimxan

*Doctoral student of Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction,
Teacher of the "Architecture" department of the Azerbaijan State Art Academy*

Abstract

Azerbaijan is a land of unique monuments that reflect different stages of the history of society. The history of Karabakh, as well as the history of Azerbaijan's statehood, is rich in very ancient monuments of material culture. This region is also considered one of the oldest human settlements in the world. Azikh cave, Guruchay, as well as Kura-Araz and Khojaly cultures replaced one another, confirmed the existence of intensive living here since ancient times, and at the same time, the historical-archaeological researches conducted here allow us to interpret all aspects of life that existed in this region. After liberation from the occupation, the material and spiritual culture of Karabakh, created during the ancient and early middle ages, increases its importance as a cultural heritage of our modern history.

Keywords: Karabakh, national identification, early medieval architecture, Caucasian Albania.

At the current stage of Azerbaijan's social and social development, the formation of national self-consciousness, the understanding of the historical past, and the protection and determination of the true value of the historical and cultural heritage are particularly relevant.

After liberation from occupation, the architectural environment formed in Karabakh for centuries allows to feel and imagine the world of distant millennia, to feel and understand the spiritual life and national identity of the Azerbaijani people who carried their will for centuries. However, it should also be noted that the destruction of documents, especially historical and cultural monuments, which tell about the history of the nation, and the burying of its heritage weakens the nation, destroys the sense of tradition, the social bond that has grown over the centuries, and makes the society prone to national degeneration.

There are architectural monuments belonging to different periods in Karabakh, which is the core of the national architectural identification of the Azerbaijani people. Unfortunately, although many of them have reached us in the form of ruins, some of them have preserved their general original appearance to some extent.

Ancient castles, rich monasteries, places of worship (temples, madrasahs, mosques, churches, etc.), residences, palace buildings, memorial monuments, caravanserais, bridges scattered throughout the territory open the way to the special and at the same time artistic world of Karabakh architecture.

Going back to the most ancient times, the study of the Azikh and Taglar monuments discovered in Karabakh as a result of archaeological excavations and belonging to the first stages of the Stone Age has also shown that the later stages of the Stone Age have passed here. Here, it is seen that the examples of the material culture of the Stone Age were primitive, but the examples of the Kura-Araz culture of the Bronze Age, which came after it, were improved and spread over a wider area. Meyntepe, Uzuntepe, Shortepe, Khachbulag, Khankendi and Garakopaktepe, which bear the characteristics of this culture, belong to this order. Guneshtepe, Khantepe, Shomultepe, and Uzerliktepe found here show that Karabakh is one of the primary centers of this culture. (photo 1)

Photo 1. Garakopaktepe. Archaeological excavations in an ancient settlement.

Khojaly-Gadabey culture archaeological monuments of the Late Bronze and Iron Age form a large group. The material and cultural monuments discovered here confirm the existence of close relations with the Southern countries. Later, Khojaly, Akhmakhin mound graves, Karabulag necropolis, etc. were added to the burial monuments. can be shown.

The ancient stone monuments discovered in the mountainous and plain areas of Karabakh - dolmens in Khojaly, cromlechs in Khankendi, as well as stone box graves from the ancient period already reflect the emergence of the ideology and spiritual way of thinking of these times.

Different religions replaced each other in Karabakh at different times. In contrast to other areas of Azerbaijan, the continuation of religious separation in Karabakh has caused great changes in the region. When Christianity was replaced by Islam in Albania, the people living in the mountainous part of Karabakh continued to worship the Christian religious ideology. It is also important to note that a large number of Armenian families were moved here from the 19th century, taking advantage of the fact that the autochthonous Albanians of Karabakh were Christians. After settling here, Armenians began to own and privatize the historical culture of those areas. Meanwhile, they called the local Albanians Gregorianized and assimilated Hayks, and considered the area "a part of the Hayk country".

In order to clarify these issues, it is necessary to refer to a somewhat ancient period and material cultural monuments, architectural and urban planning heritage should be studied again in depth. Stone column bases, capitals, tiles, etc. discovered during the archaeological excavations in Karabakh. indicates that the culture of city-building in antiquity was already developing here. The information given in ancient sources about the existence of ancient cities in the ancient territory of Karabakh - Uti and Arsak - was reflected in the research conducted in Govurgala, Barda, Ergi settlement

(Aghjabedi). The city of Barda, which foundation was laid in the ancient times in the Uti region, was already formed in this period and carried the characteristics of urban culture.

Already in the early Middle Ages, a characteristic feature of large cities was the "long walls" made up of towers and fortresses located around the city at certain intervals to prevent raids by nomadic tribes. The study of fortifications, which are generally considered to be attributes of early and medieval cities, and the identification of common similarities in their constructive and construction features (technology, building materials) allow us to follow the evolution of the urbanization of society in the early Middle Ages. The use of mud bricks and clay mass (mohr) in the construction of castle walls and towers of this period is typical for early medieval cities. The walls of the city of Çöl Aghdam in Karabakh are examples of this type. Archeological research has shown that in the Parthian-Sasanian construction technique, the dais and solid platforms were built of mud bricks or mohr. However, in early medieval Azerbaijani cities, stone was mostly used in this type of construction.

Gakhach Castle or Gachalakh Castle, one of the early medieval defensive fortifications that existed in Karabakh, is a historical-architectural monument belonging to the period of the construction of the Great Arran Monastery, located between the villages of Kolatag of Kalbajar district and Almali of Khojaly district. (Photo 2.) Chilaburt Castle or Charabert Castle is a historical-architectural monument located in Chilaburt village of Tarter region, with an area of 3 ha. There were many public buildings here, their facades were decorated with columns, and the roof was assembled in a wedge-shaped form. It has reached our time in ruins and the exact date of construction is unknown. But in the sources, the name of the castle is mentioned after the Arabs conquered Azerbaijan. Also, this castle was the residence of the Albanian prince Yesai Abu Musa.

Picture 2. Chilaburt Castle Picture 3. Gakhach Castle

In the early Middle Ages, one of the religious, political and cultural centers of Caucasian Albania was the city of Amaras. Although some medieval historians call this place a village, M. Kalankaytuklu calls Amara a city and notes that it is located in Haband district of Arsakh province. It is believed that this city was built on the site of the ancient Albanian city of Anariak. In the past, this city was called "Agoglan" by the local Muslim population. The famous researcher-scientist Z. I. Yampolski notes that the name "Agoglan" is older than "Amaras" and that this name is related to the astral religious meetings of the local population living here. [1, p. 389]

One of the main sources when studying the history of Caucasian Albania is the study of architectural features with the spread of Christianity here. Before Christianity and Zoroastrianism, the worship of the forces of nature - sun and fire, water and earth - was widespread in Albania. Albanians were considered pagans before they converted to Christianity. The Christian church was created during the formation of the feudal way in Azerbaijan, as in Albania, Georgia, and Armenia.

Numerous examples of architectural monuments that have survived to our modern times tell us about the productive work of Albanian architects. More extensive and versatile information about early medieval Albanian architecture can be found in the structure of multifaceted religious buildings. It has been shown that the first Christian religious monuments of the Caucasian Albania era were built on the banks of the Tar-Ter River. The first churches were built of wood covered with a mixture of lime and clay or straw [3, p. 9]. Later, wooden churches were replaced by stone and brick churches. However, information about wooden churches remained only in primary sources.

The monastic complex of the early Middle Ages - the Great Arran Monastery or St. Jacob's Church under another name is located in Kolatağ village of Aghdara region. This complex of the VII-VIII centuries includes two churches and two courtyards [4, p. 40]. It is located in the territory of Bina village of Khojavand region. Khutudare monastery from the early Middle Ages is located. The two churches of the complex, which have survived to our time, have a one-nave basilica form,

which is characteristic for this region. Due to its architectural features, it is assumed that the monument was built in the 5th-6th centuries.

As a result of the Christian religion maintaining its leading position in Karabakh, countless cultural monuments were built in this area. As one of these monuments, experts believe that they were built as pagan monuments, and at the same time, there are few circular temples in the South Caucasus. One of these temples is the Mokhranis temple located in Khojavand district of Karabakh region. The temple was studied by D. Akhundov. The Temple of the Seven Gates, also known by another name, was built in the Hadrud region of Nagorno-Karabakh near the village of Susanliq (Mohranis). Although the construction date is not fully specified, according to many historians, the temple belongs to the V-VI century. The temple of seven gates is the only monument belonging to a special architectural structure, the like of which cannot be found in other areas of Azerbaijan [5, p. 141-142]. Amaras Monastery, one of the sacred sanctuaries of Caucasian Albania, was an important religious center even before Christianity. The construction of this monastery complex is attributed in many sources to the IV century. The church was restored by the princes of Khachin in the 9th century, and from the 13th century it was rebuilt and turned into a monastery complex. A church with almost identical elements belonging to the Albanian churches of the early medieval period is Khudavəng. Characteristic features: rectangular shape of the exterior, broken contours of the walls in the interior and a rectangular apse. The complex, popularly called Khotaveng monastery or Khudaveng "temple of God", was the religious center of the Albanian principality of Khachin, which was established in the mountainous part of Karabakh in the 9th century after the collapse of Caucasian Albania. The territory of the church is located on the hills of Murovdag mountains and is surrounded by deep valleys. Saint Elisey church is located in the north-eastern part of the village of Sugovushan, 200 meters above sea level. The church was built in the 5th century in honor of Elisey, one of the first Christian missionaries in Albania.

Picture 4. Architectural elements of one of the cross stones in Khudavang Monastery.

Unfortunately, the examples of Christian era architecture found in Karabakh and Eastern Zangezur faced Armenian aggression, some were completely destroyed, and some were Armenianized. With the liberation of Karabakh from occupation, the main issue facing the researchers is to re-learn and study the history-architecture and urban planning traditions of this area that have existed here for centuries, and based on this information, the stylistics of the monuments, the aesthetics of the forms and images, and the national identification of Azerbaijan are completely and undoubtedly investigation of affiliation. Because national culture is based on national historical values.

References

1. Ямпольский З.И. Древняя Албания. III—I вв. до н. э. 389 səh

2. Ш.М.Мкртчян. Историко-архитектурные памятники Нагорного Карабаха (1989 год)

3. Ф.Исмаилов "Армянство против Албанской культуры" Баку 2022 115 стр.

4. Г.Мамедова "Зодчество Кавказкой Албании" Çaşıođlu 2004.

5. Д.А.Ахундов "О круглых в плане храмах Кавказкой Албании" Археологические изыскания этнографические изыскания в Азербайджане (1985 г.) Баку 1986

6. R.Göyüşov "Azərbaycan Arxeologiyası" Bakı 1986

7. <http://heritage.gov.az/az/monuments/muqeddes-yelisey-mebed-kompleksi>